

MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR ORGANIZING PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10575863>

Abstract. *In this article, the organization of professional activities today is not limited to conveying to students the information provided by the curriculum, but uses various methods to encourage students to actively participate in the educational process. change the traditional model of movement, become more interactive and create modern models of teaching, training teachers of the “new formation” and personnel capable of designing and creatively implementing the pedagogical process. It is alleged that it is aimed at preparing.*

Keywords: *research, professional activity, fundamental theory, training, modern models, artificial decomposition, integrated approach, ethical standards, design, modernization.*

Teacher education today is going through a period of serious changes, the main goal of which is to adequately assess the educational situation of a new teacher, design and creatively implement the pedagogical process. The issue of modernizing teacher education is being actively discussed.

It is possible to prepare a teacher of a “new formation” provided that modern models of teacher training are created. At Tyumen State University, one of these models (in the future “advanced”) is being successfully implemented - the integration of pedagogical and classical university education. The advantages of such education lie in the combination of fundamental theoretical and practice-oriented training of future teachers;

priority of students' research activities; clear educational and developmental potential of the educational environment and high level of teaching staff; modern educational technologies for organizing educational, quasi-professional and professional activities of students; modern forms of their extracurricular work (pedagogical clubs, creative workshops, volunteer movements, etc.), etc. All organizational, pedagogical and socio-psychological conditions created at the university are aimed at training a “new teacher”, without which it is impossible.

Solving problems of modernization of education and society as a whole. “...Projects for building a society based on innovation and the knowledge economy cannot be implemented without a “New Teacher” who can implement these projects and effectively solve the problems of student development and learning. His powers...”

Modern requirements for a teacher, as mentioned above, are reflected in professional standards that describe the qualification characteristics of a teacher and are directly related to professional standards.

For the first time, these needs are described by “work activity”, corresponding to the work functions of a teacher, in addition to knowledge and skills. Job functions include: teaching; educational activities; developmental activities that involve a significant expansion of the repertoire of activities and roles of the teacher. The need to comply with legal and ethical standards of pedagogical activity is also noted, but the standards themselves are not disclosed.

At the same time, the professional training of future teachers is built in accordance with educational standards that describe the structure of the educational process. “The educational

process in the higher education system involves not only technological, practice-oriented training, but also the formation in students of a deep understanding of the essence of the processes occurring in society, the development of the ability to discover sociocultural phenomena. That is, the modernization of teacher education involves solving the problem of the relationship between professional and educational standards that have different goals.

The solution to this problem, in turn, involves the following: modular (non-subject) construction of the basic education program (BEP); teacher training, that is, the construction of an educational model that ensures mastery of labor actions at the learning stage; development of a procedure for determining labor actions in the development and implementation of training programs for future teachers. At the same time, as A.A. Margolis pointed out [3.105], there are some “dangers” associated with a simplified concept of the tasks:

diffusion of the utilitarian and methodological component of educational training to the detriment of the scientific and theoretical one; artificial “decomposition” of integral pedagogical activity into separate types of work activity and “coaching” into separate types of work activity; the teacher’s lack of adequate preparation for the gradual “entry” into the professional community, interaction with other subjects of the educational process (“tools of culture” - the last “danger” in the assimilation of norms and rules can be prevented), pedagogical activities and values that mediate interaction in it).

At the same time, when answering the question about modern requirements for a teacher, we must not forget about the objective goal and content of education, its leading direction. In the system of “teacher-student” relationships, the teacher acts as a mediator between a person and the cultural world (the guiding function of education; in addition, a regulatory function traditionally identified in authoritarian pedagogy). values and as their realist in dialogue with the student, as the creator of the value environment and situations for choosing values.

In this regard, the objective content and purpose of pedagogical activity and communication can be characterized as helping the student, the reader in introducing him to the world of human culture, developing his personality, and forming a system of attitude towards him. different sides of reality. This interpretation combines pedagogical activity with other practical activities aimed at providing one or another assistance to a person.

The personal orientation of modern education presupposes the need to create conditions for the realization of personal resources in the educational sphere, which can only be done by those who have real experience in realizing their personal resources, that is, with a developed personality as a teacher. A.I. Subetto points out, “the quality of the individual in the educational process is a reflection of the quality of education” 3 (and I would like to add, the quality of the teacher! Education in modern conditions “requires the integral personality of the teacher, since the main instrument of the teacher’s activity is his personality, and his professional maturity allows him to find optimal solutions in constantly changing production conditions. [4]

D. A. Belukhin provides the results of empirical studies that confirm that children value teachers, first of all, for their personal qualities. “To be a beloved teacher, you must first be a Human Being.” Education in modern conditions “requires the integral personality of the teacher, since the main instrument of the teacher’s activity is his personality, and his professional maturity allows him to find optimal solutions in constantly changing production conditions. [4] D. A. Belukhin provides the results of empirical studies that confirm that children value teachers, first of all, for their personal qualities. “To be a beloved teacher, you must first be a Human Being.” At

the same time, the goals and objectives of modern teacher education are partly related to the disclosure of the personal potential of the teacher, which is reflected in the formation of certain general cultural competencies.

So, let's define the basic requirements for a modern teacher (including professional standards).

The modern methodological potential of a teacher is characterized by the following:

he is not limited to teaching others, but also engages in his own independent education;

Its work is not limited to providing students with information provided by the curriculum, but also encourages students to actively participate in the learning process using various methods. To do this, he should change the traditional model of his behavior and become more interactive;

the teacher must be able to use innovative and pedagogical technologies, since all new methods and forms of teaching are associated with them;

organizing the educational process requires certain communication skills, communication skills, flexibility, independent decision-making, and critical assessment of the results of one's activities;

In connection with the development of the Internet and distance education and the increase in the number of their users, there will be a need for special specialists - teachers who can teach them.

An integrated approach is based on ensuring the unity of development, training and education of future teachers in the process of organizing and carrying out teaching activities, communicating with its participants, knowing oneself as a future teacher, and taking on various roles in the field of professional activity. Also study the process of formation of deontological readiness as an integral system.

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